

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF LIFE CYCLE IMPACT ASSESSMENT METHODS FOR PACKAGING PRODUCTS

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doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17295142
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Abstract: *In assessing environmental impacts of packaging, it is necessary to use modern software tools, supported by verifiable databases based on the environmental life cycles of products. There are several software solutions that differ greatly from each other in terms of the complexity of life cycle modeling, accessibility to databases, LCIA methods used to determine environmental impacts, and the dynamics of database updating. The aim of this paper is to conduct LCA study for the case of a two-layered polymeric film made from low density polyethylene (PE-LD) and polyamide-6 (PA-6) laminated plastic packaging film using several LCIA methods to compare and comment the final LCA results in terms of the life-cycle environmental impacts. Results clearly show that the choice of LCIA method for evaluating environmental impacts within LCA study has a very large impact on the final result.*

Keywords: packaging, life cycle assessment, LCIA methods, environmental impacts.

1 INTRODUCTION

Without any doubt, environmental sustainability issues have become a leading trend regarding packaging development and use. Unfortunately, the simplistic view that packaging is "environmentally friendly" still prevails if it can be recycled, or if it is produced from recycled materials, still often prevails in companies and environmental NGOs. However, the environmental impacts of packaging are much more complex (Radonjič 2008; Radonjič 2014; Vergheze 2012). They occur throughout the supply chain, during use phase and during waste processing. Therefore, a more holistic thinking has been established in the European Union and elsewhere in the world when assessing the environmental impacts of packaging and packaged products, based on environmental life cycle assessments (LCA), especially since there are numerous design options of packaging products on the market produced from different materials combinations (Kan 2022; Sinnko 2024).

To determine which environmental impacts are the most harmful, or which environmental categories are the most influential and in which phase of the life cycle they occur, it is necessary to use quantitative tools for their calculation. The most popular and methodologically most sophisticated is certainly the LCA method. This complex analytical method determines the impacts of products throughout their entire life cycles, which include the extraction of raw materials, the extraction of energy sources, the production and distribution of the required energy, the production of semi-finished products, products and by-products, transport and distribution, effects during use and alternative options for handling product wastes after use.

Nowadays, many different packaging options exist on food, cosmetic and other markets. A thin flexible multilayered plastic film packaging is widely used but it is rarely suitable for recycling because it consists

of several layers of different polymeric materials which cannot be easily technically separated in an economically feasible way. However, their environmental benefits can be expressed for example through much lower use of primary resources and energy consumption among others (Bukowski 2018). However, such environmental benefits must be carefully calculated within their entire life cycle for every individual case and not generalized, especially when compared to other packaging materials options like paper, aluminium or a thicker single-material plastic options. With this regards, LCA is a powerful tool for such comparisons of environmental impacts of this types of packaging (Siracusa 2014; Tunçok-Çeşme 2024; Mousania 2025).

However, the results of LCA studies are highly dependent of different life cycle model assumptions, cut-off criteria, allocation and other aspects including the choice of the environmental impact assessment method employed in a study. This was confirmed by our own findings as well as findings from other authors which suggest that different life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) methods can lead to clearly different final results (Reap 2008; Owsianiak 2014; Tascione 2024; Bher 2024).

The aim of this paper is to conduct LCA study for the case of a laminated plastic packaging film using several LCIA methods to compare and comment the final LCA results in terms of the life-cycle environmental impacts.

2 LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT IMPACT METHODS

The determination of the environmental impacts of products in LCA studies is based on four steps (phases) defined by standard ISO 14040 (ISO 2006): goal and scope definition, inventory analysis, impact assessment and interpretaion.

More than 40 different LCIA methods are available for the implementation of the third phase, among which there are many significant differences both in terms of the scientific basis for calculating complex environmental impacts and in terms of the number of environmental categories included in the final results of the LCA analysis (PRé Consultants, 2020). The following methods are among the most well-known in practice: Ecoindicator 99 (EI99), ReCiPe 2016 and the EU Environmental Footprint (EF), which also represent stages in the development of LCIA methods. They have some common features, but also significant differences, such as the number of harmful substances and the number of environmental categories taken into account (11 for the Ecoindicator 99 method, 22 for the ReCiPe 2016 method and 27 for Environmental Footprint). Newer methods such as ReCiPe and EF are also based on better models of the action of harmful substances in the environment and in organisms, which increases their credibility or. accuracy of calculations (PRé Consultants, 2020). The ReCiPe 2016 and EF methods additionally includes water consumption and other pollution categories in the calculation, which is an important parameter for wood products. They also differ how biogenic CO₂ is considered.

What all three LCIA methods have in common is that the calculated environmental impacts can be weighted with predefined environmental weights, which allows them to be aggregated and the results presented as so-called ecopoint. Without such a calculation procedure, it would be impossible to combine different environmental categories since they are expressed in different units.. Here, 1 ecopoint represents one thousandth of the environmental burden of one EU (or world, depending on the method used) citizen in one year. Thus, an ecopoint is not an absolute value of a product's impact on the environment, but only a relative measure of the damage caused to the environment and it should be understood as a quantitative guideline for planners who want to analyze and minimize the environmental burden of their products and compare them with each other.

3 CASE STUDY

3.1 Description of packaging under study

Due to the reasons described in Introduction, two-layered polymeric film made from low density polyethylene (PE-LD) and polyamide-6 (PA-6) which is used for food packaging with the process of vacuum packing or packing in the modified atmosphere was chosen as a case for conducting LCA analysis with the aim of using different LCIA methods to study their influence on final results. Thickness of PE-LD layer is 60 μm and 30 μm for PA-6 layer.

3.2 Description of PE-LD/PA film life cycle

The LCA analysis includes the environmental impacts of oil extraction, production of organic compounds (ethylene, ϵ -caprolactam), polymerization of both polymers, film extrusion, lamination of multilayer film, welding and waste processing (Figure 1). The environmental impacts of adhesive production are also taken into account. Transport between all the aforementioned life cycle phases is included. PE-LD production takes place in Slovakia, while PA-6 production takes place in Germany. Plastic granulate is transported from both chemical industry plants to Milan to the film manufacturer, where lamination also takes place. From Milan, the laminated PE-LD/PA-6 film is transported to Ljubljana, where packaging bags are produced by heat welding. The average EU waste scenario for plastic packaging wastes was taken into consideration for determination of environmental impacts of PE-LD/PA wastes treatment.

3.2 LCA methodological aspects

The functional unit is 1m² of laminate foil, ready for package of food. Due to the limited scope of the paper, we present only part of the 'cradle-to-grave' LCA analysis, which covers the life cycle of packaging from the extraction of raw materials to the production of the packaging product.

Three different methods of life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) were used: the Econdicator 99 (H) method, which is the oldest, the ReCiPe 2016 (H), and the Environmental Footprint (EF) method. The EF method was developed as an official LCIA method to measure and communicate the life cycle environmental performance of products and organisations (European Commission 2024). On the other hand, the Econdicator 99 method is no longer being updated and is actually outdated, but surprisingly some Slovenian LCA study practitioners still use it, so we included it in the calculations for comparison. Other characteristics of LCIA methods used are given in Chapter 2.

The environmental impacts of the PE-LD/PA film were calculated using the SimaPro Analyst software tool, version 9.5.0.2 based on data on materials and processes from the internationally verified Ecoinvent database. Regarding production and consumption of electrical energy, energy mix for Slovenia was used in calculations.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A comparative analysis of different LCIA methods showed significant differences in the environmental impact results of PE-LD/PA packaging film (Table 1, Figure 2). The environmental impacts of PA-6 production are higher than those of PE-LD production regardless of the LCIA method used. The key difference between the LCIA methods is evident when comparing the impact of films extrusion with the impacts of the production of both polymer materials.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of PE-LD/PA packaging life cycle

Both recent LCIA methods (ReCiPe 2016, EF) calculate significantly higher environmental impact of the film extrusion phase compared to the environmental impacts of the production of PE-LD and PA-6. In addition, the environmental impacts of the extrusion process vary greatly depending on the LCIA method used. Very obvious differences in the calculated environmental impacts using different LCIA methods are also evident in electricity production. End-of-life phase (waste treatment and processing) was also included in LCA calculations. It was found that its contribution to the overall environmental impact of PE-LD/PA film was negligible and consequently it is not presented in Figure 2.

Figure2: Comparison of environmental impact results (in %) calculated with different LCIA methods.

Table 1: Life cycle stages of PE/PA-6 packaging and results of comparative environmental impact analysis calculated with different LCIA methods

Materials/processes	EI99 (mPt)	EI99 (%)	ReCiPe 2016 (mPt)	ReCiPe 2016 (%)	EF 3.1 (mPt)	EF 3.1 (%)
Polyethylene production	19,758	39,2	4,137	9,6	0,014	5,6
Nylon 6 production	23,058	45,7	9,380	21,9	0,024	9,7
Extrusion plastic film	3,790	7,5	12,962	30,2	0,092	36,9
Transport lorry	2,029	4,0	1,688	3,9	0,010	3,9
Laminating foil	0,921	1,8	3,429	8,0	0,024	9,8
Electricity high voltage	0,849	1,7	11,310	26,4	0,085	34,1
Total	50,405	100	42,906	100	0,249	100

5 CONCLUSIONS

To assess the environmental impacts of packaging, it is necessary to use modern analytical software tools, supported by verifiable databases. There are several software solutions available on the market, which differ greatly in terms of the complexity of product life cycle modeling, accessibility to databases, methods used to determine environmental impacts, and the dynamics of database updates.

LCA method is a powerful tool for assessing environmental impacts of packaging to obtain more objective picture whether a certain packaging option is more environmentally friendly or not. It is of particular importance in the case of more complex packaging products, which can include thin multilayer (laminated) plastic packaging.

Results of LCA study presented in this paper clearly show that the choice of LCIA method for evaluating environmental impacts within LCA study has a very large impact on the final result. Developers, designers and managers must be aware of this important fact interpreting LCA results and when considering the environmental suitability of packaging option.

The promotion of more environmentally friendly packaging must be based on credible data on environmental impacts of entire life cycles. Therefore, for the credibility of promotional and marketing materials, it is necessary to use results that have been calculated using the most modern methods and tools. For assessing the environmental impacts of packaging, we suggest using the latest LCIA methods such as the ReCiPe and/or EU Environmental Footprint method instead of the Ecoindicator 99 method.

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